

COMPARISON OF HOLOGRAPHIC, RADIOGRAPHIC, AND ULTRASONIC

TECHNIQUES FOR DAMAGE DETECTION IN COMPOSITE MATERIALS*

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Side-by-side comparisons of damage indications obtained by using tetrabromoethane (TBE) enhanced x-ray, through-transmission ultrasonic C-scan, and holographic nondestructive inspection methods on various composite specimens containing different amounts of damage are presented. Specific results are presented for (a) graphite-epoxy specimens containing fatigue induced damage regions growing from surface notches and through-the-thickness circular holes and (b) hybrid composite specimens containing static loading induced damage regions near central through-the-thickness slits. The results show that the TBE enhanced x-ray nondestructive inspection method gives the most detailed description of the damage, while the C-scans give the least information. The holographic nondestructive inspection method, using thermal loading, provides information on delaminations near the specimen surfaces and cracks in the surface plies. This information in conjunction with that provided by TBE enhanced x-ray photography gives an accurate description of the damage regions.

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Introduction

With theoretical methods for predicting the nonlinear elastic response to failure of composite laminates from basic ply properties being relatively well developed, research emphasis has shifted to developing the methodology required for designing durable and damage tolerant composite structures. The methodology must be capable of not only predicting the residual strength of composite structures containing various types of manufacturing defects and service induced damage, but also the rate of residual strength degradation as a function of fatigue loading and environment. A rational approach for developing the required damage tolerance and durability design methodology consists of (a) experimentally documenting the nature and growth induced by static and fatigue loading of damage regions from manufacturing defects and service induced damage and (b) developing stress analyses for laminates containing well documented damage. The stress analyses would relate the residual strength to the shape and size of the damage, while the damage growth documentation would lead to a damage accumulation model. With this approach in mind, we have been studying the growth of damage regions in unnotched and notched composite laminates (1,2). In addition to visual observations during static and fatigue loading tests, we have used through-transmission ultrasonic C-scan, tetrabromoethane (TBE) enhanced x-ray, and holographic non-destructive inspection methods to document the damage.

Herein, we present side-by-side comparisons of damage indications obtained by using the three nondestructive (NDI) methods on specimens containing different amounts of damage. In particular, comparative results are presented for (a) graphite-epoxy specimens containing fatigue induced damage regions growing from surface notches and through-the-thickness circular holes and (b) hybrid composite specimens containing static loading induced damage near through-the-thickness slits.

Description of the Three NDI Methods

Through-Transmission Ultrasonic C-Scan NDI Method

We used the standard through-transmission ultrasonic C-scan nondestructive inspection method (3). In this method, high frequency sound is passed through the specimen and the attenuation is monitored. The attenuation results from three sources, namely, viscoelastic effects in the resin matrix, geometric dispersion due to the heterogeneity of the composite laminates, and geometric dispersion due to internal damage such as delaminations and matrix cracks. By proper selection of the sound wave frequency, the attenuation due to delaminations and cracks can be maximized, while that due to material heterogeneity and viscoelastic effects minimized. In the present investigation, the ultrasonic instrumentation was selected to have the frequency bandwidth (10 to 18 MHz) appropriate for finding delaminations. For optimum resolution, small diameter spherically focussed transducers were used. The designated transmitter had a 12.1 cm focal length, while the designated receiver had a 1.9 cm focal length. The transducers were held facing each other at a distance of 14 cm apart in a fixture which was part of an automatic motorized scanning system mechanically connected to a recorder. The scanning mechanism was mounted on a tank of water in which the specimens were immersed. The specimens were clamped in the vertical plane defined by the coincident focal points of the transducers as the latter were scanned.

The so-called C-scan was a series of equally spaced lateral traverses of the transducers across the specimens. The electronic output discriminator circuits in the ultrasonic instrument were set to produce a dark print on the

N = 32497 37042 41617 46087 50337 54237 58637

Fig. 1 - Sequence of C-scan records showing fatigue induced delamination growth in $[(0/\pm 45/90)_S]_2$ graphite-epoxy specimen with circular hole.

recorder paper only when sound passed freely through the specimen. Attenuation of the sound beam due to damage in the specimens caused a white region within the normally dark image of the specimens on the recording. The result was a full-scan plan-view recording of the specimens showing the planar extent of the internal damage. No information on the through-the-thickness distribution of the damage was obtained.

The specimens were immersed in water to provide a uniform coupling medium to transmit the sound waves between the transducers and specimens. If the damage regions extend to the specimen boundaries, water can easily penetrate into the damage regions. Since the attenuation of sound travelling through an interface between two materials varies as the ratio of the specific acoustic impedances of the materials and the water/composite impedance ratio is much smaller than the air/composite ratio, water in the damage regions is detrimental to ultrasonic detection of damage. Hence, special precautions are required. In our investigations of fatigue induced damage regions growing from circular cutouts in $[(0/\pm 45/90)_S]_2$ graphite-epoxy laminates, the specimen edges were taped and the holes filled with putty to inhibit entry of water into the damage regions. Even with these precautions, some specimens were damaged severely enough that water could penetrate into the damage regions. In these cases, the C-scans gave distorted indications of the damage in that the C-scans showed smaller damage regions than were actually present. In fact, the damage zones could be seen to decrease in size as successive C-scans were made. An example of this phenomenon is shown in Fig. 1, which shows a sequence of C-scans for a 2.54 cm wide $[(0/\pm 45/90)_S]_2$ graphite-epoxy specimen with a 0.48 cm diameter hole. The specimen was fatigue tested using a six second trapezoidal shaped cycle (4). As can be seen from the figure, the C-scan after 50337 cycles shows a smaller damage region than the C-scan after 46087 cycles. This apparent damage healing resulted from water penetration into the specimen during the C-scanning process after 50337 cycles. Since the C-scans shown in the figure were made on different days, the apparent damage healing was not spotted until the figure was assembled.

Fig. 2 - TBE enhanced x-ray photographs showing fatigue induced damage in specimens (a) AB-63 and (b) AB-89.

For a x-ray NDI technique to show damage consisting of delaminations and cracks, the damage regions must provide a discernable contrast in the x-ray image (5,6). Since the damage regions in the graphite-epoxy and hybrid composite specimens that we examined did not provide the necessary contrast, an x-ray opaque fluid was applied to the specimens so that it could penetrate into the delaminations and matrix cracks and enhance the image of the damage on the radiograph. The fluid used in the present investigation was TBE (6). The TBE was continually applied to the surfaces of the specimen in the damaged regions for 30 minutes to give the fluid sufficient time to penetrate into all the matrix cracks and delaminations. After it had fully saturated the damage regions, the excess TBE was removed from the external surfaces of the specimen to the maximum extent possible with absorbent towels. The specimen was then laid directly on top of a Kodak type M industrial film pack and x-rayed.

Provided that the TBE can penetrate into the matrix cracks and delaminations, this enhanced x-ray technique can show extremely fine damage details. This is illustrated in Fig. 2, which shows the damage regions growing from the edges and circular holes in fatigue tested, [(0/+45/90)_S]₂ graphite-epoxy specimens. As can be seen from the figure, the damage regions consist of delaminations (diffuse splotchy areas) and a pattern of regularly spaced cracks (dark lines). The matrix crack pattern consists of regularly spaced cracks in the 90° and +45° plies with isolated cracks near the holes in the 0° plies.

Holographic NDI Method

A number of investigators have applied holographic interferometry to a variety of NDI problems for conventional structural materials. Since (7,8) contain not only an excellent summary of those efforts but also a detailed description of how holograms are made, this topic will not be treated here. It suffices to say that holography is a technique by which the image of a three dimensional object can be stored and retrieved from a two dimensional photographic emulsion. It is such an accurate recording that if two exposures are made on one emulsion with a slight distortion applied to the body being recorded between the exposures, the reconstructed light waves emanating from each of the recorded states interfere and produce a beat frequency pattern called interferometric fringes. These fringes are like lines of elevation on a contour map in that each fringe represents the locus of points on the surface of the object that have been displaced in the normal direction by a multiple of one-half the wavelength of the light used to record the hologram. For the Helium Neon laser used in our investigations, this amounts to about 0.32 μm per fringe. For NDI purposes one is interested in finding anomalies (or abrupt changes) in the fringe pattern and not in actually measuring the precise displacements everywhere on the object. If the specimen being examined is free from flaws or defects, the fringe pattern will be smooth with uniform variations. This is illustrated in Fig. 3a, which shows the fringe pattern caused by an axial compressive load on a fiberglass cylinder with a rectangular cutout. The fringe pattern is smooth with uniform variations everywhere, except in the region to the left of the cutout. In this region which is shown magnified in Fig. 3b, the fringe pattern exhibits anomalies caused by surface cracks induced during fabrication. The anomalies are of two types, namely, cusps in the fringes and lack of uniformity in the variation of the spacing between the fringes. The former type of anomaly occurs just above the lower left-hand corner and approximately two-thirds of the way up the left-hand side of the cutout, while the latter type occurs near the upper left-hand corner of the cutout.

A number of methods, each of which may produce the best fringe pattern for detecting a given flaw in a given material, are available for inducing a change in the surface of the specimen between exposures. Depending upon the

Fig. 3 - Axial compressive loading induced holographic fringe pattern showing anomalies caused by manufacturing induced surface cracks in a fiber-glass cylinder with a rectangular cutout.

specimen being examined, these include mechanical, thermal, and acoustic loading. It is difficult to give a specific set of guidelines as to which technique will work the best for a given specimen. However, some general guidelines are possible. One must always keep in mind that the goal of the loading is to produce a localized displacement normal to the surface being inspected. Thus, the thermomechanical properties of the specimen and the type and location of the damage being sought must be considered in choosing the loading technique. For example, a small crack in a metallic sheet is very difficult to find except by stretching or bending the sheet and looking for differences in displacement across the crack faces. Thermal loading would produce practically no displacement anomaly since the heat flows easily around the crack. In the case of honeycomb sandwich structures which are perhaps the easiest to inspect, thermal stressing works well since the cell walls restrain the surface except where debonds occur allowing relatively large localized displacements of the face sheet to occur.

Just as there are many possible methods for loading the specimen, the interferometric fringe patterns can be observed and recorded in a number of ways. In addition to the double exposure technique mentioned above, real time holography can be used. In real time holography, a single exposure hologram of the specimen being examined is first made. After developing and drying the emulsion, the hologram is replaced in exactly the same position that it occupied during the exposure. If the hologram and specimen being examined are simultaneously illuminated with coherent light and viewed through the hologram, one sees the actual and reconstructed surface of the specimen exactly superimposed. If the specimen is loaded to disturb its surface, a fringe

pattern is observed as in the case of the double exposure technique. This fringe pattern can be recorded by photographing the specimen through the hologram. If the loading on the specimen is changed, the fringe pattern moves and, hence, this technique can be used to examine the transient behavior of the surface of the specimen.

Real time holography is often used in conjunction with thermal loading. In this case a single exposure hologram of the unheated specimen is made, developed and properly repositioned. Then, the specimen is heated and viewed through the hologram. By heating the specimen to different temperatures, any desired fringe pattern can be recorded. For the specimens examined herein, a radiant heat source was used to raise the surface temperature of the specimens to 10°C above ambient room temperature. While real time holography was used to select the optimum temperature, all the thermally induced holographic fringe patterns presented herein were obtained by using double exposure holography.

Comparison of the Three NDI Methods

While the through-transmission ultrasonic C-scan and TBE enhanced x-ray methods are standard tools for studying damage accumulation in composite laminates (1,2,6,9-11), the holographic nondestructive inspection (HNDI) method has been seldom used. Thus, one objective of our investigation was to determine its effectiveness in documenting damage in composites. This was done by performing side-by-side comparisons of the HNDI method with the other two NDI methods on various composite specimens containing different amounts of damage.

Surface Notched Graphite-Epoxy Specimen

For our first comparison of the NDI methods, let us examine the fatigue induced damage growing from a surface notch in a $[(0/+45/0)_S]_3$ graphite-epoxy specimen (2). The specimen was 38.1 mm wide by 3.20 mm thick and had a surface notch with circular arc profile machined into it to a maximum depth of 1.6 mm using a 0.4 mm thick diamond-impregnated grinding wheel with a 10.5 mm radius and 90° included tip angle. The specimen was tested using a flight-by-flight fatigue spectrum before being inspected by the three NDI methods. The reader is referred to (2) for additional details on the specimen geometry and fatigue loading conditions.

The extent of the fatigue induced damage in the specimen is indicated in Fig. 4, which shows to the same scale the TBE enhanced x-ray photograph, C-scan record, and thermally induced holographic fringe pattern on the notched surface of the specimen. As can be seen from the figure, the TBE enhanced x-ray photograph (Fig. 4a) gives the most detailed picture of the damage which consists of delaminations, matrix cracks and fiber fractures in the surface 0° ply (2). The delaminations appear as diffuse gray regions with lighter-colored splotches in Fig. 4a, while the matrix cracks appear as a well-developed pattern of dark lines running in the fiber directions (perpendicular and at ± 45° to the surface notch). The fiber fractures in the surface 0° ply appear as (a) a short horizontal line to the left and above the left-hand tip of the surface notch and (b) a short jagged line running in a 45° direction from the right-hand tip of the notch. By comparison, the C-scan (Fig. 4b) shows only the total extent of the delamination without giving any information on the matrix cracks and fiber fractures.

The thermally induced holographic fringe pattern shown in Fig. 4c outlines the delamination region. In the figure, the fringes near the surface

Fig. 4 - (a) TBE enhanced x-ray photograph, (b) C-scan record, and (c) thermally induced holographic fringe pattern on the notched surface of a fatigue tested, surface notched, $[(0/+45/0)_S]_3$ graphite-epoxy specimen.

notch are the anomaly caused by the delamination damage. In the absence of this damage, the only fringes that would have been present are the two light vertical fringes to the sides of the surface notch. The unusual convergence of fringes above and to the left of the left notch tip can be interpreted as showing the fiber fracture region in the surface 0° ply, but it should be noted that without the x-ray photograph (Fig. 4a) for comparison this interpretation would be speculative at best. Moreover, Fig. 4c gives no information on the matrix cracking. Finally, it should be noted that Fig. 4c was our first attempt at using thermal loading holography for documenting damage in composites.

Specimens with Through-the-Thickness Circular Holes

For our next set of comparisons, let us look at two examples of fatigue induced damage growing from through-the-thickness circular holes in $[(0/+45/90)_2]_2$ graphite-epoxy specimens (1). The specimens were 2.54 cm wide with centrally located 0.48 cm diameter circular holes. The specimens were fatigue tested at different maximum cyclic load levels using the six second trapezoidal shaped cycle described in (4). Specimen AB-63 (tested at a maximum load of 15000 N) was inadvertently buckled after 21997 cycles and then nondestructively inspected, while specimen AB-89 (tested at a maximum cyclic load level of 12500 N) survived 118267 cycles and was then inspected.

The extent of fatigue induced damage in specimen AB-63 is shown in Figs. 5 and 2a. Figures 5a through 5d show to the same scale the TBE enhanced x-ray photograph, C-scan record, thermally induced holographic fringe pattern on the front surface of the specimen, and thermally induced holographic fringe pattern on the back surface as viewed through the specimen from the front, respectively; while, Fig. 2a shows an enlarged view of a different TBE enhanced x-ray photograph of the same specimen. As can be seen from these figures, the TBE enhanced x-ray NDI method gives the most detailed picture of the damage which consists of fiber fractures, matrix cracks, and delaminations. The fiber fractures, caused by buckling of the specimen, appear as short jagged dark lines near the top ends of the matrix cracks running in the vertical (0° fiber) direction in Figs. 2a and 5a. The delaminations appear as diffuse dark gray regions with lighter-colored splotches, while the matrix cracks appear as a well developed pattern of dark lines running in the fiber directions. The degrees of definition of the delaminations and matrix cracks shown in Figs. 2a and 5a are different. This is a direct consequence of the different exposure times used in x-raying the specimen. Hence, one must be careful in interpreting damage patterns defined by TBE enhanced x-ray radiography because the details that can be seen depend on the exposure time. The longer exposure x-ray photograph (Fig. 5a) shows the full extent of the matrix cracking in the regions outside the delaminations, while the shorter exposure x-ray photograph (Fig. 2a) defines the matrix cracking within the delaminated region. Moreover, the longer exposure x-ray photograph indicates that some of the delaminated regions consist of more than one delamination. By comparison, the C-scan record (Fig. 5b) only shows the planar extent of the delaminated regions.

The thermally induced holographic fringe patterns shown in Figs. 5c and 5d provide information on delaminations and matrix cracks that cannot be obtained from either the C-scan record or TBE enhanced x-ray photograph. As can be seen from Figs. 5c and 5d, the holographic fringe patterns on the two surfaces of the specimen are different. Since holographic fringe patterns are contour maps of displacements (normal to the specimen surface) induced by the thermal loading, the differences in the fringe patterns provide information on the depth of the delaminations. Thus, the delaminations outlined by the anomalies in the fringe pattern shown in Fig. 5c are near the front sur-

Fig. 5 - (a) TBE enhanced x-ray photograph, (b) C-scan record, (c) thermally induced holographic fringe pattern on front surface, and (d) thermally induced holographic fringe pattern on back surface (as viewed through the specimen from the front) of specimen AB-63.

face of the specimen, while those outlined in Fig. 5d are near the back surface. This is all that can be said about the location of the delaminations without any knowledge of the stacking sequence of the specimen and damage mechanisms in composites. Since this information is available for this specimen, the long narrow fringe anomaly below the circular hole in Fig. 5d can be interpreted as a delamination between the back surface 0° and adjacent 45° ply. The edges of the anomaly are matrix cracks in the back surface 0° ply. The other fringe anomalies shown in Fig. 5d are most likely delaminations between the 45° and 90° plies nearest to the back surface of the specimen. This interpretation is consistent with visual observations of the specimen edges. Likewise, the fringe pattern anomalies near the specimen edges shown in Fig. 5c are delaminations between the 45° and 90° plies closest to the front surface. The anomalies near the circular hole in Fig. 5c are more difficult to interpret. Since evidence of surface matrix cracking (vertical lines two-fifths of the way from the hole to the left edge of the specimen and just to the right of the hole) is present and the specimen is known to have been buckled, the anomalies near the hole are most likely delaminations between the front surface 0° and underlying 45° plies. Delaminations between the subsurface 45° and 90° plies are also present, but these are masked by the delaminations between the surface 0° and underlying 45° plies.

The extent of fatigue induced damage in specimen AB-89 is shown in Figs. 2b and 6. Figures 6a through 6d show to the same scale the TBE enhanced x-ray photograph, C-scan record, thermally induced holographic fringe pattern on the front surface of the specimen, and thermally induced holographic fringe pattern on the back surface as viewed through the specimen from the front, respectively; while, Fig. 2b shows an enlarged view of the TBE enhanced x-ray photograph. As can be seen from these figures the TBE enhanced x-ray photograph gives the most detailed picture of the damage, while the C-scan record gives the least detailed information. The holographic fringe patterns help locate the delaminations and surface ply matrix cracks and, hence, they supplement the results. The damage consists of (a) closely spaced matrix cracks in the 90° plies (clearly visible horizontal lines in Figs. 2b and 6a), (b) closely spaced matrix cracks in some of the 45° plies (barely discernable 45° lines in Figs. 2b and 6a), (c) matrix cracks in the front surface 0° ply (well defined vertical dark lines in Figs. 2b and 6a and vertical fringe anomaly boundaries in Fig. 6c), (d) matrix cracks in the back surface 0° ply (dark vertical lines in Figs. 2b and vertical fringe anomaly boundaries in Fig. 6d), (e) delaminations between the front surface 0° and underlying 45° plies to the sides and below the circular hole (splotchy regions in Figs. 2b and 6a and fringe pattern anomalies in Fig. 6c), (f) delaminations between the back surface 0° and underlying 45° plies to the sides and above the circular hole (splotchy regions in Figs. 2b and 6a and fringe anomalies in Fig. 6d), (g) delaminations between the 90° and adjacent 45° plies near the circular hole (presence of 45° and 90° lines in the splotchy regions near the hole in Figs. 2b and 6a), and (h) delaminations between the 90° and adjacent 45° plies near the specimen edges (splotchy regions in Figs. 2b and 6a and fringe pattern anomalies in Figs. 6c and 6d). Most of the delaminations near the left edge of the specimen are near the back face (larger anomalous fringe regions near the left edge in Fig. 6d than in Fig. 6c), while those near the right edge are mostly near the front face (larger anomalous fringe regions near the right edge in Fig. 6c than in Fig. 6d).

Specimens with Through-the-Thickness Slits (Cracks)

For our last set of comparisons, let us look at four examples of static load induced damage near through-the-thickness slits simulating cracks in various hybrid laminates. The specimens were instrumented with clip-on gages across the slits and loaded in tension until the slit opening displacement vs.

a

b

c

d

Fig. 6 - (a) TBE enhanced x-ray photograph, (b) C-scan record, (c) thermally induced holographic fringe pattern on the front surface, and (d) thermally induced holographic fringe pattern on back surface (as viewed through the specimen from the front) of specimen AB-89.

load records indicated the presence of damage. The specimens were then unloaded and inspected using the three NDI methods. The extent of damage in the specimens is shown in Figs. 7 through 11. Figure 7 shows enlarged TBE enhanced x-ray photographs of the damage in specimens ACB-11 and AIB-5. Views a through d in Figs. 8 through 11 show to the same scale the TBE enhanced x-ray photograph, C-scan record, thermally induced holographic fringe pattern on the front surface of the specimen, and thermally induced holographic fringe

Fig. 7 - TBE enhanced x-ray photographs of specimens (a) ACB-11 and (b) AIB-5.

pattern on the back surface as viewed through the specimen from the front, respectively.

Specimen ACB-11. Specimen ACB-11 was a $(0/+45/0)_S$ graphite/S-glass/epoxy hybrid with the 0° and $+45^\circ$ plies being graphite-epoxy and S-glass-epoxy, respectively. The specimen was 50.8 mm wide by 1.1 mm thick and had a 19.8 mm long slit perpendicular to the loading (0° fiber) direction. It was loaded to a gross section stress of 245 MPa, unloaded and nondestructively inspected.

Figures 7a and 8 show the results obtained by the three NDI methods. As can be seen from the TBE enhanced x-ray photographs (Figs. 7a and 8a) and C-scan record (Fig. 8b), the S-glass fibers were not very uniformly distributed within the 45° plies. The S-glass fiber bundles appear as nonuniform gray bands in the x-ray photographs and light diagonal lines in the C-scan

Fig. 8 - (a) TBE enhanced x-ray photograph, (b) C-scan record, (c) thermally induced holographic fringe pattern on the front surface, and (d) thermally induced holographic fringe pattern on the back surface (as viewed through the specimen from the front) of specimen ACB-11.

record. The fact that the S-glass fiber bundles are visible in the x-ray photographs makes interpretation of the damage details more difficult, but not impossible. Moreover, the approximately rectangular gray boundaries with internal circular spots above and below the slit in Figs. 7a and 8a are the outline of the adhesive, used in bonding the clip-on gage, remaining on the specimen surface. The residual adhesive appears as a light rectangular boundary in Fig. 8b and is clearly visible in Fig. 8d.

Upon examining Figs. 7a and 8, we see that the damage is confined to the vicinity of the slit tips with the damage region near the left tip of the slit being larger than that near the right tip. The damage region near the right slit tip consists of matrix cracks and delaminations with no evidence of fiber fractures. With one exception the matrix cracks in the 0° plies (vertical lines in Figs. 7a and 8a) are not discernable within the fringe anomalies in Figs. 8c and 8d and, hence most of them are within the inner 0° plies. The only exception is the right most crack in Figs. 7a and 8a, which can be identified in Figs. 8c and 8d. Thus, it is within both the back and front surface 0° plies. The delamination (dark triangular region in Figs. 7a and 8a, light triangular region in Fig. 8b, and fringe anomalies in Figs. 8c and 8d near the right slit tip) is most likely between the plus and minus 45° plies. Matrix cracks are probably present in the 45° plies, but they cannot be seen in any of the figures.

The damage region near the left slit tip consists of matrix cracks, delaminations, and fiber fractures. The matrix cracks in the 0° plies above the right slit tip (vertical lines in Figs. 7a and 8a) do not produce an anomaly in the fringe patterns in Figs. 8c and 8d and, hence, they are within the inner 0° plies. The matrix cracks running in the 0° direction below the slit tip did produce a fringe pattern anomaly in Figs. 8c and 8d and, hence, they are in the surface 0° plies. The matrix cracks in the front surface 0° ply terminate in a fiber fracture region (jagged horizontal line below the right slit tip in Fig. 7a and fringe anomaly in Fig. 8c). The presence of the fiber fractures is confirmed by visual observation. There is also evidence of fiber fractures on the back surface (the unusual anomaly in the fringe below and to the left of the left slit tip in Fig. 8d). Matrix cracks running in the 45° directions from the left slit tip (sharp black 45° line below the slit tip and a broad 45° band above the slit tip in Figs. 7a and 8a, and 45° fringe anomalies in Figs. 8c and 8d) are present. The delamination region appears as a splotchy region in Figs. 7a and 8a, light region in Fig. 8b, and fringe anomalies in Figs. 8c and 8d.

Specimen AIB-5. Specimen AIB-5 was a $(0/+45/0)_s$ graphite/Nomex/epoxy hybrid with the 0° and $+45^\circ$ plies being graphite-epoxy and Nomex-epoxy, respectively. The specimen was 25.4 mm wide by 1.07 mm thick and had a 10.3 mm long slit perpendicular to the loading (0° fiber) direction. It was loaded to a gross section stress of 401 MPa, unloaded and nondestructively inspected.

Figures 7b and 9 show the results obtained by the three NDI methods. As can be seen from these figures, there is considerable damage near the slit tips. Extensive regions of delamination, fiber fracture, and matrix cracking can be seen near both slit tips. The damage region near the left slit tip consists of (a) broken front surface 0° fibers (jagged horizontal line to the left and below the left slit tip in Fig. 7b and fringe anomaly in Fig. 9c), (b) broken back surface 0° fibers (jagged horizontal line to the left and above the left slit tip in Fig. 7b, fringe anomaly in Fig. 9d, and visual observation), (c) matrix cracks in the front surface 0° ply (vertical lines in Figs. 7b and 9c), (d) matrix cracks in the 45° plies (diagonal lines in Fig. 7b), and (e) delaminations between the plies (splotchy area in Figs. 7b and 9a, light region in Fig. 9b, and fringe pattern anomalies in Figs. 9c and 9d). The damage near the right slit tip consists of (a) a well defined crack

Fig. 9 - (a) TBE enhanced x-ray photograph, (b) C-scan record, (c) thermally induced holographic fringe pattern on the front surface, and (d) thermally induced holographic fringe pattern on the back surface (as viewed through the specimen from the front) of specimen AIB-5.

in the back surface 0° ply (fairly long jagged line emanating from the slit tip in Figs. 7b and 9a and an anomalous fringe that seems to follow the crack in Fig. 9d), (b) fractured fibers in the front surface 0° ply (short jagged line emanating from the slit tip in Fig. 7b and fringe anomaly in Fig. 9c), (c) matrix cracks in the surface and interior 0° plies (vertical lines in Figs. 7b, 9a, 9c, and 9d), (d) matrix cracks in the 45° plies (diagonal lines in Figs. 7b and 9a), and (e) delaminations between the plies (splotchy regions in Figs. 7b and 9a, light area in Fig. 9b, and fringe anomalies in Figs. 9c and 9d). From the fringe anomalies in Figs. 9c and 9d, we can conclude that most of the delaminations and cracks in the 0° plies are near the back surface of the specimen.

Specimen AHA-4. Specimen AHA-4 was a $(0/+45/0)_S$ Kevlar/graphite/epoxy

Fig. 10 - (a) TBE enhanced x-ray photograph, (b) C-scan record, (c) thermally induced holographic fringe pattern on the front surface, and (d) thermally induced holographic fringe pattern on the back surface (as viewed through the specimen from the front) of specimen AHA-4.

hybrid with the 0° and $+45^\circ$ plies being Kevlar-epoxy and graphite-epoxy, respectively. The specimen was 25.4 mm wide by 1.09 mm thick and had a 10.5 mm long slit perpendicular to the loading (0° fiber) direction. It had vertical gaps in the 0° plies resulting from poor quality fabrication. The specimen was loaded to a gross section stress of 243 MPa, unloaded and inspected.

Figure 10 shows the results obtained by the three NDI methods. The TBE enhanced x-ray photograph (Fig. 10a) shows no damage, while the C-scan (Fig. 10b) and holographic fringe patterns (Figs. 10c and 10d) show features that could be interpreted as damage. The vertical band in Fig. 10b is actually a defect (gaps between the fibers on both the back and front surfaces of the specimen) in the laminate induced during manufacturing and not damage caused by the loading. The long vertical fringe pattern anomalies in Figs. 10c and

Fig. 11 - (a) TBE enhanced x-ray photograph, (b) C-scan record, (c) thermally induced holographic fringe pattern on the front surface, and (d) thermally induced holographic fringe pattern on the back surface (as viewed through the specimen from the front) of specimen AHA-5.

10d show additional manufacturing defects. It should be noted that without the TBE enhanced x-ray photograph for comparison the fringe pattern anomalies would have been interpreted as matrix cracks in the surface 0° plies. Close examination of the fringe patterns near the slit tips (Figs. 10c and 10d) indicates the presence of small anomalies at the slit tips. These anomalies can be interpreted as delaminations between the surface and subsurface plies. This interpretation is consistent with visual observations of the specimen surfaces.

Specimen AHA-5. Specimen AHA-5 had the same stacking sequence as specimen AHA-4. The specimen was 25.4 mm wide by 1.14 mm thick and had a 10.5 mm long slit perpendicular to the loading (0° fiber) direction. It also had a manufacturing defect (gap between the fibers on the back surface). The

specimen was loaded to a gross section stress of 312 MPa, unloaded and non-destructively inspected.

Figure 11 shows the results obtained by the three NDI methods. As can be seen from the figure, the damage near the slit is extensive and consists of matrix cracks, delaminations, and fiber fractures. The fractured fibers in the subsurface 45° plies appear as dark lines emanating from the slit tips and running in neither a 0° or 45° direction in Fig. 11a. Based on the fringe pattern anomalies in Figs. 11c and 11d, these cracks seem to be closer to the back surface of the specimen. The matrix cracks in the surface 0° plies appear as dark vertical lines in Fig. 11a and cusps in the fringes near the slit in Figs. 11c and 11d. The matrix cracks in the subsurface 45° plies appear as isolated and very closely spaced 45° lines in Fig. 11a. The delaminations appear as gray regions with lighter-colored splotches in Fig. 11a and anomalous fringe patterns in Figs. 11c and 11d. The manufacturing defect appears as a vertical band in Fig. 11b and vertical line in Fig. 11d. Thus, this defect is on the back surface of the specimen.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Based on the comparisons of the three nondestructive inspection methods presented in the preceding section, we see that:

(1) TBE enhanced x-ray photography gives the most detailed information on the nature and planar distribution of damage in composites. It is capable of finding fiber fractures, matrix cracks, and delaminations.

(2) Holography using thermal loading shows delaminations and cracks in the surface plies. It is capable of finding both matrix cracks and fiber fractures in the surface plies and providing information on the through-the-thickness distribution of the delaminations.

(3) Through-transmission ultrasonic C-scans show the planar extent of delaminations without giving any information on either matrix cracks or fractured fibers.

(4) None of the three NDI methods that we compared give a complete picture of the damage in composites.

Based on our experience with the three NDI methods, we have the following recommendations:

(1) A x-ray opaque fluid that is not as toxic as TBE should be found and used in future applications of the enhanced x-ray NDI method.

(2) A procedure for using enhanced x-ray photography for getting information on the through-the-thickness distribution of damage in composites should be developed. Some of this desirable information can be obtained by x-raying the specimen edgewise (9) or making stereo pair x-ray photographs of the specimen. It may also be possible to construct a three dimensional x-ray image of the damage by using tomography. These methods should be investigated.

(3) The holographic NDI method shows potential for documenting damage in composites, but needs further development. More work needs to be done in interpretation of fringe pattern anomalies and selection of loading methods for best damage resolution. Specifically, damage indications obtained using thermal, acoustic, and mechanical loading techniques need to be studied to establish criteria for selecting the most appropriate of these for finding

and defining damage in composites.

(4) It appears feasible to apply the holographic NDI method to a specimen in a test frame, thereby simplifying periodic inspection during damage growth studies. This should be investigated.

(5) Since the through-transmission ultrasonic C-scan method gives very limited information on damage in composites, it should not be used for damage documentation purposes. Instead, more sophisticated acoustic imaging techniques (e. g., the pulse-echo method) should be used.

(6) Until a fully satisfactory NDI method for obtaining an accurate picture of damage in composites is developed, a combination of NDI methods should be used.

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